

CASCADE FUNDING CALL 2

SELECTED PROJECTS OVERVIEW

The graphic features three overlapping white circles, each containing a collection of logos from various partner organizations and universities. The logos include:

- Left Circle:** CYENS, EMBL, HOCHSCHULE OSNABRÜCK, ALMA MATER STIHKORUM UNIVERSITA DI BOLOGNA, ue-firedi, EXECUTIVE AGENCY FOR HIGHER EDUCATION, RESEARCH, DEVELOPMENT AND INNOVATION FUNDING, MAX DELBRÜCK CENTER, LIU LINKÖPING UNIVERSITY, 150, SEAMK, IRB BARCELONA, FORTH, ANECA, THE UNIVERSITY OF EDINBURGH, UNIVERSITÉ CLERMONT AUVERGNE, 1958, NWO, museo galileo, and KARELIA University of Applied Sciences.
- Middle Circle:** CYENS, HOCHSCHULE OSNABRÜCK, ALMA MATER STIHKORUM UNIVERSITA DI BOLOGNA, ue-firedi, EXECUTIVE AGENCY FOR HIGHER EDUCATION, RESEARCH, DEVELOPMENT AND INNOVATION FUNDING, MAX DELBRÜCK CENTER, LIU LINKÖPING UNIVERSITY, 150, SEAMK, IRB BARCELONA, FORTH, ANECA, THE UNIVERSITY OF EDINBURGH, UNIVERSITÉ CLERMONT AUVERGNE, 1958, NWO, museo galileo, and KARELIA University of Applied Sciences.
- Right Circle:** Lodz University of Technology, LIU LINKÖPING UNIVERSITY, universidade de aveiro, University of Suffolk, University of Bedfordshire, Amsterdam UMC, Federation of Finnish Learned Societies, UNIVERSITY OF TURKU, UCC, LAPIN AMK, RDA, TOBB ETÜ, amU, UNIVERSIDADE CATOLICA PORTUGUESA, and UAM Universidad Autónoma de Madrid.

Second Call for CoARA Boost Cascade Funding

Selected Projects Overview

Cascade Funding Call 2
Selected Projects Overview

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General Information

In mid-July 2025, the second round of projects was selected as part of the first call for Cascade Funding.

The 28 selected projects introduce diverse starting points and approaches through three types of supported projects. These reflect different stages of an institution's reform journey, namely:

- **Institutional Pilot Projects** allow organizations to test new assessment models and approaches in targeted areas, fostering experimentation with tools like IT workflows, qualitative KPIs, and open science metrics. Each project may receive up to €30,000 for a period of one-year.
- **Teaming Projects** facilitate knowledge exchange between up to three different organizations with varying levels of expertise, enabling mutual growth and best practice sharing. These projects are funded up to €40,000 for one year.
- **Institutional Change Projects** support more comprehensive reform by refining or creating new assessment structures aligned with the commitments of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment. These projects can receive up to €60,000 for a duration of one-year.

Over 140 applications have been received for the 2nd Call of the Cascade Funding, among which, 28 have been selected and supported by CoARA Boost with this following repartition per project type:

Figure 1: Types of Projects Selected for Call 2

With the following geographical diversity of projects per country:

Geographical Diversity of Projects Per Country:

Figure 2: Geographical Diversity of Projects per Country for Call 2

In the following pages of the present booklet, each project is introduced with its key elements and the nature of its alignment with the Agreement.

Please note that the projects are not listed or ranked in any order of importance.

List of the Cascade Funding Call 2 Beneficiaries: Institutional Pilot Projects

Name of the project	Organisations	Countries	Pages
CoARaverse in Psychology. Piloting reforms to foster and assess diverse research cultures with a focus on participation, qualitative indicators, and peer-review.	Sigmund Freud Private University	Austria	6
Assessment Tool for evaluating the qualitative impact of RDI activities at Universities of Applied Sciences	Karelia University of Applied Sciences	Finland	8
Leveraging the local research evaluation system to raise awareness at the University of Bologna	Alma Mater Studiorum – Università di Bologna	Italy	11
Adoption by Example: Reflecting Open Research Progress to Guide Transformations in Assessment	University of Edinburgh	United Kingdom	13
From skills to recognition: A pan-EMBL Data Stewardship Programme for the Research Assessment Reform	European Molecular Biology Laboratory (EMBL)	Germany	15
APRO – Architectural Projects as Research prOducts: towards shared assessment criteria	ProArch	Italy	17
Transforming Research Assessment at CYENS: Towards a Responsible, Inclusive and Impact-Driven Model (TRAC)	CYENS Centre of Excellence	Cyprus	19
FairEval: Developing Fair and Responsible Research Assessment Models at IRCCS of Reggio Emilia	Azienda USL IRCCS di Reggio Emilia	Italy	22
Advancing Research Assessment in Serbia: A Pilot Project for the Institute of Economic Sciences – ARISE	Institute of Economic Sciences	Serbia	24
RECAST – Reforming Evaluation Criteria for Assessment, Science, and Teams	Max Delbrück Center (MDC)	Germany	26
Responsible Indicator Framework for Humanities and Social Sciences	FHSS of the University of Zagreb	Croatia	28

Cascade Funding Call 2: Selected project 1/28

Organisation overview	
<p>Sigmund Freud Private University Vienna, Austria</p> <p><i>Austria's largest HEI, Sigmund Freud Private University (SFU) comprises the faculties of Psychotherapy Science, Psychology, Medicine, and Law, conducting research at multiple international sites: Vienna, Linz (Austria), Berlin, Ljubljana, Milan and Paris.</i></p>	

The Project
Type
<input type="checkbox"/> Teaming project <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Institutional Pilot Project <input type="checkbox"/> Institutional Change Project
Title
CoARaverse in Psychology. Piloting reforms to foster and assess diverse research cultures with a focus on participation, qualitative indicators, and peer-review.
Abstract
<p>CoARaverse aims at piloting research assessment reform at the Faculty of Psychology of Sigmund Freud Private University. To account for the faculty's diverse research cultures, research assessment reform will focus on participatory engagement, qualitative indicators and peer review. Through "participatory contact zones", a CoARaverse working group will be engaged in reforming three assessment instruments at both the individual and the faculty level: The Research Report depicting SFU's research output on an annual basis will be reformed with a focus on qualitative KPIs and a specifically developed reporting workspace in the Research Information System (RIS) Pure. The Development Interview, conducted annually by Deans with faculty researchers, will be further developed through a portfolio-based approach aiming at supporting sustainable, inclusive, and individualised research careers by recognizing research profile relevant competencies and diverse contributions, including "research-related care practices". The External Research Evaluation of the faculty will be piloted and will be based on formative guiding questions instead of target values, and on external peer-review. The added value will be a new workspace template in RIS Pure and a development interview template recognising research-related care practices. After the pilot phase, CoARaverse research assessment practices will be extended from a faculty to a university level.</p>
Mission and objectives. How does the project fits with the overall vision of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment?

CoARaverse overall mission is to reform SFU's research assessment practices along the principles and commitments of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment, focusing on participation, qualitative indicators, and peer-review. Objectives are to reform three key instruments:

- I. The Research Report (RR) depicts SFU's research output on an annual basis. CoARaverse will extend the value of the report beyond the quantitative criteria used until now. To this end, qualitative KPIs and a special reporting workspace in RIS PURE will be developed.
- II. The Development Interview (DI), conducted annually by deans with faculty researchers, will be further developed through a portfolio-based approach. This aims to support sustainable, inclusive, and individualised research careers by assessing research profile relevant competencies and diverse contributions, and by recognising "research-related care practices". Guidelines and tools will be designed to reflect diverse researcher paths, and the timing of assessments will ensure strategic value.
- III. The External Research Evaluation (ERE) of SFU faculties is conducted once every six years, based on formative guiding questions instead of target values, and on external peer-review. CoARaverse will specify its guiding questions, revise stakeholder involvement in the process and develop the self-report's structure, including qualitative KPIs and a "narrative CV of the faculty".

ARRA core commitments' supported by the Project

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Recognise the diversity of contributions to, and careers in research according to the needs and the nature of the research
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer-review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Abandon inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal and publication-based metrics, in particular inappropriate uses of journal impact factor (JIF) and h-index
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations in research assessment

Cascade Funding Call 2: Selected project 2/28

Organisation overview	
<p>Karelia University of Applied Sciences Joensuu, Finland</p> <p><i>An educational and research organisation in applied research by training experts in a multidisciplinary manner.</i></p>	

The Project
Type
<input type="checkbox"/> Teaming project <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Institutional Pilot Project <input type="checkbox"/> Institutional Change Project
Title
Assessment Tool for evaluating the qualitative impact of RDI activities at Universities of Applied Sciences
Abstract
<p>One objective of Karelia University of Applied Sciences' CoARA action plan is to enhance the qualitative assessment of RDI activities and make their impact more visible. This project aims to achieve this by designing and implementing an assessment tool to integrate responsible evaluation throughout the life cycle of Karelia RDI projects, from planning to completion.</p> <p>The project is linked to improving Karelia UAS's operational quality. Audits by the Finnish Education Evaluation Centre (FINEEC) for 2018–2024 identified clarifying societal interaction and impact objectives and developing indicators as key targets for universities of applied sciences. Karelia recognized the need, especially in RDI activities, noting that impact assessment is unsystematic and lacks clear processes or tools, with primary focus on measures rather than impact.</p> <p>The Assessment Tool will help define desired impacts, select measures to achieve them, monitor objectives, and assess project impacts. It will be integrated into Karelia UAS's enterprise resource planning (ERP) system. To our knowledge, such a tool is not employed in Finnish universities of applied sciences, which is why it is being developed and piloted in this project. The tool will be openly shared for use by others in international and national CoARA networks.</p>
Mission and objectives. How does the project fits with the overall vision of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment?
CoARA focuses on the diversity and openness of research work and its evaluation, promoting actions that strengthen the quality and impact of scientific investigations. The central aim of this project is to enhance the methodologies used in assessing research quality and impact.

In universities of applied sciences, research activities are practically oriented and conducted in collaboration with industry. Businesses actively utilize the knowledge generated in Research, Development and Innovation (RDI) projects during the project's lifecycle. To accurately evaluate this unique characteristic, qualitative assessments are necessary to achieve a high level of excellence.

The assessment tool for RDI projects will be designed to identify biases in research and development activities. By examining the societal impact over the long term, the tool can trace significant and enduring effects of the university of applied sciences' RDI projects. It is also essential to evaluate the ongoing and tangible interactions between the university's RDI projects and industry, as these daily interactions can lead to immediate influences and potentially develop into substantial long-term impacts.

The CoARA commitment emphasizes the responsible use of quantitative indicators to support evaluation when relevant and appropriate, acknowledging that this is context-dependent. In this pilot project, qualitative indicators are developed to complement quantitative metrics, enabling a comprehensive evaluation of the impact of RDI projects in these universities. Throughout the project's duration, an assessment tool is designed and implemented to integrate responsible evaluations across all stages of Karelia UAS's RDI projects, from initial planning to completion. This tool employs specified quantitative and qualitative indicators.

Our assessment tool utilizes the principles outlined in the San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment (DORA) guidelines for responsible quantitative assessment. This means that the application of quantitative metrics must be tailored to the specific context of the evaluation. A thorough evaluation must incorporate both quantitative and qualitative indicators. To date, a systematic qualitative assessment of the impact has not been conducted in Karelia University of Applied Sciences RDI projects, and the quantitative assessment has been insufficient in certain respects. The aim of this project is to develop a tool that facilitates a systematic, comprehensive, and responsible evaluation of RDI activities, thereby ensuring a more accurate and plausible assessment of their effectiveness and impact.

Karelia University of Applied Sciences will implement a pilot study to evaluate a tool designed for responsible research assessment. Upon the tool's integration for broader application across universities of applied sciences, the pilot study results will be disseminated. This dissemination will occur through both international and national cooperation networks, in which Karelia University of Applied Sciences actively participates, to further the development of responsible research evaluation methodologies. Consequently, the Finnish Career Assessment Matrix (FINCAM) is utilized and applied in the development of the evaluation tool.

ARRA core commitments' supported by the Project

- | | |
|-------------------------------------|---|
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> | Recognise the diversity of contributions to, and careers in research according to the needs and the nature of the research |
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| <input type="checkbox"/> | Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations in research assessment |

Cascade Funding Call 2: Selected project 3/28

Organisation overview	
<p>Alma Mater Studiorum – Università di Bologna Bologna, Italy</p> <p><i>The University of Bologna hosts over 96,000 students in 5 campuses and comprises 31 departments (over 3400 researchers) covering virtually all academic disciplines. Committed to excellence in education, research, and societal engagement, its strategic plan emphasizes equity, sustainability, and open science.</i></p>	 ALMA MATER STUDIORUM UNIVERSITÀ DI BOLOGNA

The Project
Type
<input type="checkbox"/> Teaming project <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Institutional Pilot Project <input type="checkbox"/> Institutional Change Project
Title
Leveraging the local research evaluation system to raise awareness at the University of Bologna
Abstract
<p>The project aims at leveraging the current system employed by the University of Bologna (UNIBO) for internal research assessment and monitoring (VRA – University Research Evaluation) to raise awareness on CoARA’s reform. Although UNIBO was among the early signatories of CoARA and is co-chairing the Italian National Chapter, it struggles to implement the reform, due to external and internal challenges. The biggest internal challenge is UNIBO’s dimension and the diversified nature of its academic community: 31 departments, 5 campuses, over 3400 researchers, virtually all disciplines covered.</p>
Mission and objectives. How does the project fits with the overall vision of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment?
<p>To address this challenge, we build on UNIBO’s long experience in evaluating internal research activities, by planning to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Milestone 1: analyze how the results of the current VRA system are employed by the different Departments and disciplinary areas, fostering the exchange of best practices and awareness-raising on CoARA principles (cf. CoARA commitment 1); - Milestone 2: initiate a discussion on CoARA principles within the University Research Evaluation Committee (CVRA), responsible for VRA (cf. COARA commitments 2,3,6); - Milestone 3: organize a final event, open to the whole community but esp. targeting early career researchers, for disseminating the project’s results and

further fostering the discussion on CoARA's reform at the national level (cf. CoARA commitment 7).

ARRA core commitments' supported by the Project

- | | |
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| <input type="checkbox"/> | Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations in research assessment |

Cascade Funding Call 2: Selected project 4/28

Organisation overview	<p data-bbox="1082 456 1382 533">THE UNIVERSITY of EDINBURGH</p>
<p data-bbox="204 315 544 349">University of Edinburgh</p> <p data-bbox="204 356 608 389">Edinburgh, United Kingdom</p> <p data-bbox="204 398 1054 571"><i>The University of Edinburgh - Edinburgh, UK is a top-5 research-intensive university in the UK, with ~18,000 staff and 49,000 current students. UoE is in the forefront of Open Research in the UK, including as an active member of the League of European Research Universities (LERU) and the UK Reproducibility Network (UKRN)</i></p>	

The Project
Type
<p data-bbox="209 748 491 781"><input type="checkbox"/> Teaming project</p> <p data-bbox="209 790 596 824"><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Institutional Pilot Project</p> <p data-bbox="209 833 655 866"><input type="checkbox"/> Institutional Change Project</p>
Title
<p data-bbox="204 927 1385 1001">Adoption by Example: Reflecting Open Research Progress to Guide Transformations in Assessment</p>
Abstract
<p data-bbox="204 1061 1390 1314">The University of Edinburgh (UoE) is renowned for its expertise in Open Research (OR). Its data management policy and OR Roadmap emphasize sharing and reusability and encourages researchers to adopt FAIR practices, supported by an award-winning library team. UoE also hosts experts in open, social, and data sciences, like the present co-applicants from STIS and BioRDM. However, UoE's assessment of researchers does not mention Open Research.</p> <p data-bbox="204 1323 1390 1839">By combining our expertise, we will provide and promote the assessment of Open Research at both individual and organisational levels. We will first evaluate Open and FAIR sharing of research outputs in at least three pilot projects, using a scalable, validated process. Second, we will discuss the results and their implications with researchers, research managers, using external collaborative input from the University of Leiden. Finally, we will share the project's outcomes across UoE, our formal and informal networks and beyond, highlighting leading institutes and researchers to help embed Openness in research culture. We aim to influence local researcher evaluation by updating a specific field in the standardized, University-wide process for academic staff promotions. Gaining agreement to update this component offers an achievable way to recognize Open and FAIR outputs, aligned with CoARA's goals.</p>
Mission and objectives. How does the project fits with the overall vision of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment?
<ul data-bbox="209 1942 1385 2016" style="list-style-type: none"> - Objective-1: Pilot a scalable assessment of research output Openness across Medicine, Biological Sciences and Social sciences at UoE. Using the open-

source, text-mining software ODDPub we will screen publications to determine if data or code was shared. This analysis will identify data sharing trends, compare openness across institutes and highlight researchers leading OR practices, in line with CoARA's commitments to focus on quality, impact and recognition of contributions beyond traditional metrics.

- Objective-2: Iterative discussion of Obj.1 results. We will discuss results with pilot group managers to gain feedback and compare OR practices and adoption across disciplines. Experts in OR assessment from CWTS Leiden will contribute in person (<https://www.cwts.nl/>) to give a broad perspective in this discussion and also a report for dissemination.
- Objective-3: Wider output dissemination and institutional engagement. The report from Obj.1-2 will be shared and discussed widely through the UoE in strategic seminars/meetings in collaboration with the Head of Research Cultures, and the Research Data Support Officer.

Recommendations from this project will be embedded in our Research Cultures Action Plan and OR Roadmap, to propose new guidance that includes OR in researcher evaluation.

ARRA core commitments' supported by the Project

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Cascade Funding Call 2: Selected project 5/28

Organisation overview	
<p>European Molecular Biology Laboratory (EMBL) Heidelberg, Germany</p> <p><i>EMBL leads European life science research, operating across six sites with shared research programmes. As CoARA signatory and member, EMBL commits to advancing the research assessment reform. This is reinforced by EMBL's Open Science Policy, promoting reproducible research and the recognition of diverse research contributions.</i></p>	

The Project
<p>Type</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Teaming project <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Institutional Pilot Project <input type="checkbox"/> Institutional Change Project</p>
<p>Title</p> <p>From skills to recognition: A pan-EMBL Data Stewardship Programme for the Research Assessment Reform</p>
<p>Abstract</p> <p>This project will implement a comprehensive Data Stewardship (DS) Programme at EMBL to identify, train, and recognise staff with data stewardship responsibilities. This heterogeneous group includes technicians, computational specialists, supporting staff, and researchers with de facto DS roles but lack formal recognition. Emphasis will be placed on early-career professionals, for whom DS represents a promising but overlooked career path. The pilot represents the first step towards professionalising and enhancing recognition of DS as an essential scientific activity, safeguarding the value of data among research outputs and highlighting the importance of rewarding these skills and contributions.</p> <p>The programme addresses both education and recognition of DS activities through complementary approaches: (1) training staff in effective data design and handling practices, (2) increasing awareness, among participants and across EMBL, of the essential role of data-related contributions in research, (3) informing EMBL about educational and resource needs of data stewards, and of inclusive research assessment practices that account for such roles. Deliverables will include educational and outreach materials, a reusable training curriculum, a mapping of DS roles across EMBL (to seed a community around this topic), and recommendations for embedding DS into assessment practices and scaling the programme across institutions.</p>
<p>Mission and objectives. How does the project fits with the overall vision of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment?</p>

Monitoring of EMBL’s Open Science (OS) Policy adoption (2022–2024) showed increases in preprints, datasets, and software, but low uptake of Data Management Plans, suggesting OS practices are often applied retrospectively. This reflects limited investment in data design, likely due to skill gaps and a lack of recognition. EMBL’s RRA and OS frameworks inform this project’s aim: to upskill and value data-focused roles and embed inclusive, cross-site practices aligned with CoARA principles. Data Stewardship (DS) is positioned as a core element of responsible, forward-looking research planning.

This project will pilot a DS Training Programme that enhances data-related practices and research data outputs within EMBL. The pilot enables the implementation of good practices and OS policies through targeted education and institutional integration. This pilot will:

1. Develop a training programme to build skills in data handling, documentation, and visibility, ensuring public and reusable training materials
2. Deliver the programme to one cohort to gather feedback and measure impact
3. Embed peer review of DS practices into the programme structure, seeding a community of data stewards, mentors, managers, and training developers
4. Inform actionable guidelines for evaluating DS contributions in RRA
5. Deliver a scalable model for implementation across EMBL and other institutions

This initiative directly addresses commitments in the Agreement by recognising the diversity of data-related research contributions, developing qualitative methods to evaluate such contributions, and reducing reliance on journal-based metrics by recognising and empowering a broader range of research outputs. By creating structured methods to evaluate DS practices and data outputs, this pilot project helps ensure that staff receive appropriate credit for all aspects of their work supporting the research ecosystem.

ARRA core commitments’ supported by the Project

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Recognise the diversity of contributions to, and careers in research according to the needs and the nature of the research
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<input type="checkbox"/>	Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations in research assessment

Cascade Funding Call 2: Selected project 6/28

Organisation overview	
<p>ProArch – Società Scientifica Nazionale dei Docenti di Progettazione Architettonica</p> <p>Rome, Italy</p> <p><i>ProArch is the Italian Learned Society of Architectural Design professors. It fosters national exchange among members, and represents them at institutions such as CUN, ANVUR, EU etc., also contributing to the definition of criteria for the assessment of the quality of the related scientific products (design theory and practice).</i></p>	

The Project	
Type	
<input type="checkbox"/> Teaming project <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Institutional Pilot Project <input type="checkbox"/> Institutional Change Project	
Title	
APRO – Architectural Projects as Research prOducts: towards shared assessment criteria	
Abstract	
<p>APRO aims to provide a shared definition of the criteria for assessing an architectural project as a research product.</p> <p>APRO intends to address how to describe the scientific methodology of project production. The aim is to detail what is currently outlined by ANVUR in the guidelines published on the occasion of the VQR 2020–2024, which opens up the possibility of submitting architectural projects for evaluation.</p> <p>APRO is structured in three phases. The main field of experimentation is the Calls for Projects organized by ProArch, which are opportunities for members to exchange ideas concerning specific themes and places through project practice. While the first phase aims to define a state-of-the-art inside and outside the academic environment, the second phase will be a collective exercise implemented through the ongoing Call for Projects organized in Genoa and the one planned in 2026 in Cagliari.</p> <p>The practice of self-evaluation based on the methodological description of one’s project is proposed as a first step to increase evaluation skills through a more conscious peer-review process, progressively. Specific attention will be required to the correlation between images and texts, which is central to the online platform planned in the third phase.</p>	
Mission and objectives. How does the project fits with the overall vision of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment?	

APRO aims to progress in defining the architecture project's assessment criteria as a research product.

The aim is to catalyze good practices and innovate research assessment tools starting from what the “Agenzia Nazionale di Valutazione del sistema Universitario e della Ricerca” (ANVUR) has undertaken in the framework of the “Valutazione della Qualità della Ricerca” (VQR 2020–2024). Consistent with ARRA, the inter-institutional relationship between ProArch and ANVUR aims at systemic changes with medium- and long-term trajectories and impacts.

Coherent with the reform journey outlined in the ARRA, the APRO proposal includes:

- 1st phase: it aims to share the reform journey with the members. Research on research will primarily concern analyzing current evaluation practices, engaging researchers at all career stages.
- 2nd phase: it will involve members of the ProArch scientific community within a Call for Projects through co-operation between assessors and assesses by developing existing and designing new assessment criteria and processes based on the critical analysis of the state-of-the-art.
- - 3rd phase: it aims to test and verify new assessment criteria, tools, and processes, proposing a digital infrastructure fostering the practice of data sharing within ProArch and the entire scientific community towards an inter-institutional and international cooperation.

ARRA core commitments' supported by the Project

<input type="checkbox"/>	Recognise the diversity of contributions to, and careers in research according to the needs and the nature of the research
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<input type="checkbox"/>	Abandon inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal and publication-based metrics, in particular inappropriate uses of journal impact factor (JIF) and h-index
<input type="checkbox"/>	Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations in research assessment

Cascade Funding Call 2: Selected project 7/28

Organisation overview	
<p>CYENS Centre of Excellence Nicosia, Cyprus</p> <p><i>CYENS is the leading Centre of Excellence in Cyprus for Interactive Media, Smart Systems and Emerging Technologies. As a collaboration between research institutions and the Municipality of Nicosia, CYENS serves as an innovation hub supporting interdisciplinary research and impact-driven solutions in line with European R&I policies. CYENS hosts over 100 researchers across 20+ multidisciplinary research groups and acts as a bridge between academia, industry, and society to drive innovation and impact.</i></p>	

The Project	
Type	
<input type="checkbox"/> Teaming project <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Institutional Pilot Project <input type="checkbox"/> Institutional Change Project	
Title	
Transforming Research Assessment at CYENS: Towards a Responsible, Inclusive and Impact-Driven Model (TRAC)	
Abstract	
<p>CYENS Centre of Excellence proposes a one-year institutional pilot project to introduce a responsible research assessment process aligned with the CoARA Agreement and guided by the SCOPE framework. As a pioneering Centre of Excellence in Cyprus, CYENS will become a regional leader in institutionalising values-led, context-sensitive, and evidence informed evaluation. The reform process will follow the 5 SCOPE stages, start with what you value, consider the context, explore existing evidence, probe deeply, and evaluate, ensuring the framework aligns with both international standards and the local research culture.</p> <p>In addition to the SCOPE approach, CYENS will implement several tools and practices outlined in Annex 4 of the CoARA Agreement. This includes piloting narrative CV formats, incorporating responsible metrics guidance, and applying structured peer-review rubrics developed by CoARA WGs. These elements will support systemic reform while also enabling comparability and knowledge exchange across institutions.</p> <p>The initiative will co-design, pilot, and embed a revised assessment framework that recognises diverse research contributions, prioritises qualitative peer review, and promotes responsible use of metrics. It will build internal capacity through training and consultation, culminating in a formal Action Plan for long-term adoption. Outcomes will include a validated institutional framework, updated</p>	

policies, narrative CV templates, and a public dissemination campaign. The pilot will position CYENS as a transfer hub of best practices, offering replicable models for other Centres of Excellence in Cyprus and across Europe.

Mission and objectives. How does the project fit with the overall vision of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment?

The mission of this project is to transform CYENS's approach to research evaluation by embedding responsible practices institution-wide. Anchored in the SCOPE framework and supported by CoARA's Annex 4 Toolbox, the reform will foreground institutional values such as inclusivity, innovation, interdisciplinarity, and societal impact. It will build a sustainable assessment model that reflects CoARA's principles and reinforces CYENS's strategic role in the European Research Area (ERA). The project's objectives are to:

- Develop an evaluation framework based on values, context, and stakeholder engagement (SCOPE: Start with what you value, Consider the context).
- Leverage international examples (DORA, CoARA, LERU) and apply outputs from CoARA WGs such as peer review rubrics, narrative CV guidelines, researcher profile descriptors, and self-assessment checklists (Explore existing evidence).
- Pilot the new approach through training, mock evaluations, and staff engagement using the SCOPE framework and selected tools from Annex 4 (Probe deeply).
- Evaluate effectiveness, institutional impact, and community reception using both qualitative and quantitative methods (Evaluate).
- Finalise and institutionalise the framework through an endorsed Action Plan and national dissemination.

By applying the SCOPE process and leveraging the practical tools of CoARA's Annex 4, including those focused on improving peer-review transparency, fair recognition of interdisciplinary and collaborative work, and qualitative indicators, CYENS will lead a strategic and replicable institutional reform, strengthening internal practices while contributing to national and EU-wide assessment transformation.

ARRA core commitments' supported by the Project

- Recognise the diversity of contributions to, and careers in research according to the needs and the nature of the research
- Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer-review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators

- | |
|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Abandon inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal and publication-based metrics, in particular inappropriate uses of journal impact factor (JIF) and h-index |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations in research assessment |

Cascade Funding Call 2: Selected project 8/28

Organisation overview	
<p>Azienda USL IRCCS di Reggio Emilia Reggio Emilia, Italy</p> <p><i>The IRCCS in Reggio Emilia, part of the Local Health Authority of Reggio Emilia, is a leading research cancer center. It drives innovation from prevention to palliative care, with research playing a central role in bringing new cancer therapies and technologies into clinical practice</i></p>	

The Project
Type
<input type="checkbox"/> Teaming project <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Institutional Pilot Project <input type="checkbox"/> Institutional Change Project
Title
FairEval: Developing Fair and Responsible Research Assessment Models at IRCCS of Reggio Emilia
Abstract
<p>This pilot project takes place within an Italian research hospital following Ministry of Health guidelines for research evaluation, emphasizing quantitative indicators over qualitative and context-sensitive criteria. The project aims to explore alternative methodologies aligned with the COARA principles, promoting systemic reform through inclusive, participatory, and co-creative approaches. The initiative involves approximately 50 researchers at all career stages (PhD candidates, fixed-term staff, and permanent researchers) ensuring broad representation across disciplines, genders, and employment types. Through a literature review, participatory focus groups, and a Delphi process, the project will co-develop indicators that prioritize epistemic diversity, gender equity, open science, and underrecognized contributions. It will also address the responsible use of bibliometric indicators.</p> <p>A multidisciplinary team, including a grant officer, an administrative professional involved in the evaluation process, an information specialist, and an expert in qualitative methods, will coordinate the project. Focus groups will serve as spaces for reflecting on current practices and co-designing fairer assessment models.</p> <p>Delphi study will refine and prioritize indicators, followed by retrospective testing on real researcher profiles.</p> <p>Ultimately, the project aims to produce a replicable local model—particularly relevant for other Italian Health Research Institutes, that contributes meaningfully to the cultural transformation envisioned by COARA’s European agenda.</p>

Mission and objectives. How does the project fits with the overall vision of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment?

This project aims to develop fairer, inclusive research assessment practices within an Italian Health Research Institute. Through participatory methods, it fosters cultural change, values diverse contributions, and promotes responsible use of metrics, producing a replicable model. The project aligns with CoARA's commitments in multiple ways. It ensures inclusivity by involving researchers at all career stages and from diverse disciplines and employment types. It values epistemic diversity, gender equity, and the recognition of underrepresented contributions in the development of research assessment indicators. Another key focus is recognizing the misuse of metrics in current evaluation frameworks and the need to refine new evidence-based metric practices. Transparency and accountability are central to the project's methodology, with participatory focus groups and a Delphi process creating open spaces for dialogue and shared decision-making. The project addresses potential unintended consequences of new assessment systems by identifying tensions and testing indicators on real researcher profiles. It brings together expertise from information science, qualitative research, and evaluation, fostering an integrated, collaborative approach. By combining qualitative and quantitative methods, the project moves beyond a purely numerical focus. Its final goal is to foster institutional change and cultural transformation, sharing results to spread best practices within the wider research community

ARRA core commitments' supported by the Project

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|-------------------------------------|---|
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> | Recognise the diversity of contributions to, and careers in research according to the needs and the nature of the research |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> | Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer-review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> | Abandon inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal and publication-based metrics, in particular inappropriate uses of journal impact factor (JIF) and h-index |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> | Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations in research assessment |

Cascade Funding Call 2: Selected project 9/28

Organisation overview	
<p>Institute of Economic Sciences Belgrade, Serbia</p> <p><i>The Institute of Economic Sciences (IES) is a public scientific research institution focused on advancing knowledge in macroeconomics, labor and welfare, digital economy, innovation economics, environmental economics, and economic history and theory.</i></p>	

The Project
Type
<input type="checkbox"/> Teaming project <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Institutional Pilot Project <input type="checkbox"/> Institutional Change Project
Title
Advancing Research Assessment in Serbia: A Pilot Project for the Institute of Economic Sciences – ARISE
Abstract
<p>The ARISE project aims to develop and pilot a qualitative, peer-review-based research assessment model at the Institute of Economic Sciences (IES) in Serbia, aligned with the CoARA commitments. It addresses key shortcomings in the national framework, which relies heavily on quantitative metrics – a system widely criticized across disciplines, especially by social sciences institutes. By co-creating an inclusive model with researchers and leadership, ARISE shifts the focus from individual publication counts to the performance of research departments, emphasizing quality, societal relevance, and impact. The model will be piloted through self-assessment reports and external peer reviews, engaging researchers across career stages. An interdisciplinary Advisory Board with representatives from all scientific fields will guide broader relevance and future adaptation.</p> <p>The project will initiate model adoption across Serbia’s 11 social science institutes (employing around 350 researchers) and serve as a strategic entry point for wider national reform. Scalable tools, guidance, and policy recommendations will be produced to support future reforms.</p> <p>As the only CoARA signatory in Serbia, IES will build on its leadership and previous initiatives, in particular two national forums on research assessment organized in 2024, which positioned the Institute as a key driver of national reform efforts.</p>
Mission and objectives. How does the project fits with the overall vision of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment?
The mission of the ARISE project is to lead research assessment reform in Serbia by developing and testing a qualitative, peer-review-based model at the

Institute of Economic Sciences (IES), aligned with core CoARA commitments. The project addresses major shortcomings of Serbia's current evaluation system, which relies heavily on quantitative metrics. This approach is particularly inadequate in the social sciences, where research impact is often societal and policy oriented. ARISE will pilot the model across IES's six research departments, focusing on research quality, impact, diversity, and collaboration, and shifting emphasis from individual output quantity to collective contributions. The model will be co-developed with IES researchers, tested through self-assessment reports and external peer reviews, and refined through feedback.

The project has three main objectives: 1) Develop and validate the model at IES in close collaboration with internal stakeholders and with strategic input from the external interdisciplinary Advisory Board; 2) Initiate adoption of the model by other social science institutes through the sharing of tools, methods, and lessons learned; 3) Create the foundation for broader scaling by preparing the model for adaptation to other scientific fields, supported by the Advisory Board (AB) and targeted outreach mechanisms. In parallel, ARISE will deliver evidence-based recommendations to the Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation (Ministry) to support future reforms of the national research assessment framework.

ARRA core commitments' supported by the Project

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Recognise the diversity of contributions to, and careers in research according to the needs and the nature of the research
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer-review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Abandon inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal and publication-based metrics, in particular inappropriate uses of journal impact factor (JIF) and h-index
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations in research assessment

Cascade Funding Call 2: Selected project 10/28

Organisation overview	
<p>Max Delbrück Center for Molecular Medicine (MDC) Berlin, Germany</p> <p><i>The MDC is a leading biomedical research institution in Germany, committed to translating discoveries into novel diagnostics and treatments. It hosts over 70 research groups in the life sciences, fostering interdisciplinary and translational approaches.</i></p>	

The Project
Type
<input type="checkbox"/> Teaming project <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Institutional Pilot Project <input type="checkbox"/> Institutional Change Project
Title
RECAST - Reforming Evaluation Criteria for Assessment, Science, and Teams
Abstract
<p>In today's rapidly evolving research landscape—particularly within the life sciences—traditional metrics such as impact factors and citation counts fail to reflect the full breadth and depth of researchers' contributions. With RECAST, the Max Delbrück Center (MDC) proposes a holistic reform of its internal and external peer review processes to better capture the complexity of contemporary biomedical research and recognize diverse forms of excellence.</p> <p>We will design, pilot, and institutionalize a new framework for assessing researchers and research units, grounded in the values of team science, Open Science, mentorship, translational impact, and community engagement. A central feature of this reform is the implementation of narrative CVs supported by a digital contributions database and a new set of co-developed, contextualized KPIs.</p> <p>Open Science will be a core evaluation criterion, encompassing FAIR data practices, open access publishing, software/code sharing, and reproducibility initiatives. The framework will promote early, inclusive, and responsible knowledge sharing.</p> <p>Rooted in the MDC2030 strategy and aligned with CoARA principles, RECAST aims to transform research assessment from a narrow, metric-based exercise into a reflective, transparent, and inclusive practice—creating a scalable model for systemic change across Europe.</p>
Mission and objectives. How does the project fits with the overall vision of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment?
RECAST embodies the CoARA vision by fostering a research assessment system that values quality, diversity, and collaboration over traditional metrics.

Our objectives are to:

1. Reform the MDC's internal and external evaluation processes for research Group Leaders in full alignment with CoARA commitments.
2. Co-design new qualitative and contextualized indicators (i.e. KPIs), with a specific focus on: Team contributions, Active participation in Open Science, Mentorship as a cornerstone for nurturing the next generation of researchers
3. Introduce and pilot revised research criteria for transparent and fair assessment of MDC researchers.
4. Foster a cultural shift through training concepts and materials for reviewers, enabling the rapid adoption of the new assessment framework
5. Engage with European partners to integrate and harmonize these approaches with existing strategies in EU networks, supporting long-term institutionalization.

The project will unfold in five phases: evaluating current practice (WP1), stakeholder engagement and co-design (WP2), alpha testing (WP3), institutional rollout and further dissemination (WP 4 & 5). Our long-term vision is to establish RECAST as a scalable and transferable model for biomedical research institutions across Europe.

ARRA core commitments' supported by the Project

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Recognise the diversity of contributions to, and careers in research according to the needs and the nature of the research
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer-review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators
<input type="checkbox"/>	Abandon inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal and publication-based metrics, in particular inappropriate uses of journal impact factor (JIF) and h-index
<input type="checkbox"/>	Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations in research assessment

Cascade Funding Call 2: Selected project 11/28

Organisation overview	
University of Zagreb Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences Zagreb, Croatia <i>FHSS, with a tradition of 150 years, is the largest higher education and research institution in Croatia in social sciences and humanities. It offers 114 study programmes (BSc, MSc and PhD), participates in the national Open Science infrastructures, and is a national coordinator for four ERICs (CESSDA, CLARIN, EHRI, ESS).</i>	

The Project
Type
<input type="checkbox"/> Teaming project <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Institutional Pilot Project <input type="checkbox"/> Institutional Change Project
Title
Responsible Indicator Framework for Humanities and Social Sciences
Abstract
<p>This project presents a participatory, purpose-driven catalogue of indicators designed to support transparent and responsible research assessment in the Humanities and Social Sciences (HSS). Developed through a cocreation process involving diverse stakeholders, the catalogue offers a structured, context-sensitive framework for the use of indicators aligned with the principles of Open Science.</p> <p>Each indicator is clearly defined and accompanied by information on its intended use, data sources, collection methods, and limitations. Governance elements are fully integrated: for every indicator, responsible organisational units and individuals are identified, along with procedures for data collection, quality control, and regular updates. This ensures that indicators are not only technically sound but also contextually appropriate.</p> <p>The framework is especially attentive to the needs of non-Anglophone research communities, taking into account linguistic, cultural, and infrastructural diversity. By supporting inclusivity and transparency in assessment practices, the project contributes to a more equitable and open research ecosystem in HSS.</p> <p>The catalogue will be piloted at the University of Zagreb Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences (FHSS), providing a real-world testing ground for refining its design, usability, and institutional fit. Insights from this pilot will inform further development and potential broader adoption in other institutions with similar research contexts.</p>

Mission and objectives. How does the project fits with the overall vision of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment?

- Develop a context-sensitive and participatory catalogue of indicators that recognises the diversity of contributions in HSS, and reflects the epistemic cultures, languages, and practices of non-Anglophone communities.
- Promote the responsible use of quantitative indicators by ensuring that each indicator in the catalogue is clearly defined and transparent in its purpose and linked to well-documented data sources, limitations, and appropriate governance mechanisms.
- Discourage the inappropriate use of journal- and publication-based metrics by offering alternative indicators more suitable for diverse outputs and impacts of HSS research. The project will also provide clear guidance on the limitations of such legacy metrics.
- Pilot the catalogue of indicators at the institution, committing resources for its implementation, testing, and refinement. The pilot will serve as a model for institutional change and provide insights into scaling the approach.
- Engage researchers and institutional stakeholders in the co-design and review of assessment criteria, tools, and processes, ensuring that all elements are adapted to the local context and have the legitimacy and relevance required for long-term adoption.
- Raise awareness and build capacity for reform through workshops and communication materials to support transparent understanding of assessment criteria and the responsible use of indicators while encouraging a culture of openness and continuous improvement.

ARRA core commitments' supported by the Project

- | | |
|-------------------------------------|---|
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> | Recognise the diversity of contributions to, and careers in research according to the needs and the nature of the research |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> | Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer-review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> | Abandon inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal and publication-based metrics, in particular inappropriate uses of journal impact factor (JIF) and h-index |
| <input type="checkbox"/> | Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations in research assessment |

List of the Cascade Funding Call 2 Beneficiaries: Teaming Projects

Name of the project	Organisations	Countries	Pages
DIVERSE+: Advancing Diverse and Qualitative Research Assessment Across Europe	Lodz University of Technology* Linköping University University of Aveiro	Poland* Sweden Portugal	31
Reforming Research Assessment: Building Inclusive, Open, and Equitable Evaluation Practices through Open Educational Resources	University of Suffolk* University of Bedfordshire	United Kingdom* United Kingdom	34
Implementing Framework for Assessment: Case FIN-CAM	Federation of Finnish Learned Societies* Lapland University of Applied Sciences University of Turku	Finland* Finland Finland	36
Laboratory of Engagement with Research Assessment Reform (LERAR): exchanging good practices between three members of one European university alliance, CIVIS	University of Bucharest* Universidad Autonoma de Madrid Aix-Marseille University	Romania* Spain France	38
Teaming for self-evaluation in research assessment across scales: from researchers to institutions	Research Data Alliance Association* Catholic University of Portugal TOBB University of Economics and Technology	Belgium* Portugal Türkiye	41
ORFIRA - Introducing an Open Research Framework and integrating Open Research indicators into Research Assessment	University College Cork AmsterdamUMC	Ireland* The Netherlands	44

* Refer to the coordinator of the consortium

Cascade Funding Call 2: Selected project 12/28

Organisation overview	
<p>Lodz University of Technology (TUL) Lodz, Poland</p> <p><i>TUL is a leading institution merging scientific research with innovation. TUL conducts research in 12 scientific disciplines. It was the first technical university in Poland to receive the HR Excellence in Research award (2016). Signing CoARA (2022) reinforces its commitment to responsible, transparent research evaluation.</i></p> <p><u>Partner organisations:</u></p> <p>Linköping University (LiU) Linköping, Sweden</p> <p><i>LiU is a public institution, one of Sweden's largest academic centers. Renowned for its focus on multidisciplinary education and research, it is committed to attractive career paths for future researchers. It is actively involved in the HRS4R award, signing CoARA (2022) marks significant progress in this area.</i></p> <p>University of Aveiro (UAveiro) Aveiro, Portugal</p> <p><i>UAveiro is a leading institution in Portugal, strongly emphasizing research, innovation and interdisciplinary collaboration, with key role in S&T in the region and at national/international levels. Signed COARA (2024), and it supports more qualitative, transparent and diverse methods of assessing research and researchers.</i></p>	

The Project
Type
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Teaming project <input type="checkbox"/> Institutional Pilot Project <input type="checkbox"/> Institutional Change Project
Title
DIVERSE+: Advancing Diverse and Qualitative Research Assessment Across Europe
Abstract
<p>Three institutions (Lodz University of Technology-PL, Linköping University-S and University of Aveiro-PT) have partnered together to reach the common goal of beneficial knowledge and experience sharing. They belong to the European University Alliance ECIU-European Consortium of Innovative Universities where a specific CoARA working group has been appointed with the specific task to promote and facilitate common learning processes. The DIVERSE+ proposal aims to pilot a structured scheme for exchanging practices among these three ECIU</p>

institutions, facilitating mutual learning and mutual improvement for two CoARA core commitments: recognition of diversity of contributions to research, and the research assessment based primarily on qualitative evaluation. The results and outputs can be replicable by the other 10 ECIU partners and provide, at a larger scale, a reinforcement of COARA commitments in a European University alliance. The proposal has 3 specific objectives: O1. Foster awareness of COARA principles and commitments and engage the three University communities in the change/cultural shift of research assessment; O2: Foster institutional change through a sustainable network of knowledge exchange, training and collaboration: O3. Develop guiding principles and best practices for diverse and qualitative research assessment to be shared with the other 10 ECIU members, maximising the impact of the proposal.

Mission and objectives. How does the project fits with the overall vision of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment?

The three institutions belong to the European University Alliance ECIU-European Consortium of Innovative Universities whose Vice Presidents for Research recently decided to set up a CoARA working group with the specific task of promoting knowledge sharing, providing mutual expertise and supporting institutions that are not proceeding at the same pace concerning the CoARA commitments. This proposal aims to pilot a more structured scheme for exchanging practices among three ECIU institutions, facilitating mutual learning and mutual improvement and results and outputs can be replicable by the other 10 ECIU partners providing, at a larger scale, a reinforcement of COARA commitments in a European University alliance. The proposal has 3 specific objectives: O1. Foster awareness of COARA principles and commitments and engage the three University communities in the change/cultural shift of research assessment, in particular for the recognition of diverse contributions to, and careers in research, and the for a research assessment primarily based on qualitative evaluation with central peer-review; O2: Foster institutional change through a sustainable network of knowledge exchange, training and collaboration: O3. Develop guiding principles and best practices for diverse and qualitative research assessment to be shared with the other 10 ECIU members, maximising the impact of the proposal.

ARRA core commitments' supported by the Project

- Recognise the diversity of contributions to, and careers in research according to the needs and the nature of the research
- Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer-review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators

- | |
|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Abandon inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal and publication-based metrics, in particular inappropriate uses of journal impact factor (JIF) and h-index |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations in research assessment |

Cascade Funding Call 2: Selected project 13/28

Organisation overview	
<p>University of Suffolk Ipswich, United Kingdom</p> <p><i>The University of Suffolk, offers state-of-the-art facilities, high-quality teaching, and strong graduate prospects. Its mission is to serve as a model for a new type of civic university, deeply embedded in its communities, and driving societal and economic change through transformation, collaboration, and choice</i></p> <p><u>Partner organisation:</u> University of Bedfordshire Luton, United Kingdom</p> <p><i>The University of Bedfordshire is an internationally recognised and award-winning institution with a heritage of quality education going back more than 100 years. It believes in nurturing students to become educated, employable and entrepreneurial global citizens.</i></p>	

The Project
Type
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Teaming project <input type="checkbox"/> Institutional Pilot Project <input type="checkbox"/> Institutional Change Project
Title
Reforming Research Assessment: Building Inclusive, Open, and Equitable Evaluation Practices through Open Educational Resources
Abstract
<p>This project aims to develop an Open Educational Resource (OER) toolkit to support a cultural shift in research assessment, aligned with the CoARA principles to provide early career researchers, principal investigators, and institutional leaders with the necessary knowledge and skills to implement responsible research assessment and open science practices. It will promote the recognition of diverse research contributions and career paths, prioritising qualitative evaluation with peer review at its core, and discouraging inappropriate use of journal- and publication-based metrics such as JIF and h-index.</p> <p>Developed in collaboration with the University of Bedfordshire (UK), the OER-toolkit will include interactive training guides, online learning modules, case studies, and video resources to build capacity in open science, covering Open Science Principles, Open Research Cultures, data management, open data, FAIR principles, and data stewardship, to ensure scalability and adaptability across different institutional contexts.</p>

This initiative directly supports CoARA’s commitment to reforming research assessment and aligns with the UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science. The OER-toolkit will contribute to a more equitable and transparent research culture, enhancing institutional readiness for open science mandates while fostering responsible and inclusive assessment practices.

Mission and objectives. How does the project fits with the overall vision of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment?

This project aims to support the transformation of research assessment by developing an OER-toolkit that supports institutions, researchers, and assessors in adopting responsible and transparent evaluation practices. The toolkit will facilitate the exchange of good practices, drive reform in assessment frameworks, and promote innovative approaches aligned with ARRA.

Aimed at early-career researchers, principal investigators, institutional leaders, peer reviewers, and assessment committees, the OER-toolkit will enhance knowledge and skills in open science and responsible research assessment, providing training, raising awareness, and offering practical guidance to ensure fair and inclusive evaluation of research contributions.

The project aligns with key CoARA principles by:

- Recognising diverse research contributions and career paths (P1);
- Prioritising qualitative evaluation over journal-based metrics (P2);
- Eliminating inappropriate use of JIF and h-index (P3);
- Committing resources to reform through training and support for assessors (P5);
- Promoting transparency, awareness, and the exchange of good practices (P7, P8);
- Ensuring assessment practices are evidence-based and informed by open data (P10).

Developed in collaboration with the University of Bedfordshire (UK), the OER-toolkit will be openly accessible, adaptable, and scalable, enabling institutions to embed responsible research assessment within their policies and practices.

ARRA core commitments’ supported by the Project

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| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> | Recognise the diversity of contributions to, and careers in research according to the needs and the nature of the research |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> | Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer-review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> | Abandon inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal and publication-based metrics, in particular inappropriate uses of journal impact factor (JIF) and h-index |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> | Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations in research assessment |

Cascade Funding Call 2: Selected project 14/28

Organisation overview	
<p>Federation of Finnish Learned Societies Helsinki, Finland</p> <p><i>The Federation of Finnish Learned Societies (TSV), established in 1899, is a national co-operative body for learned societies in Finland. It contributes to the co-operation between learned societies, supports and develops scholarly communication and publishing, and promotes awareness and usage of research results.</i></p> <p>Partner organisations:</p> <p>Lapland University of Applied Sciences Rovaniemi, Finland</p> <p><i>Lapland University of Applied Sciences is the northernmost UAS in Finland and in the EU focusing on higher education and research, development and innovations. Lapland UAS capitalises on the strengths and opportunities of its changing operating environment to develop expertise and vitality for the needs of northern operators.</i></p> <p>University of Turku Turku, Finland</p> <p><i>The University of Turku is an international multidisciplinary research university that provides students with innovative problem-solving skills and high-standard education based on latest research.</i></p>	UNIVERSITY OF TURKU

The Project
Type
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Teaming project <input type="checkbox"/> Institutional Pilot Project <input type="checkbox"/> Institutional Change Project
Title
Implementing Framework for Assessment: Case FIN-CAM
Abstract
<p>The project advances responsible researcher assessment by co-piloting the implementation of the Finnish Career Assessment Matrix (FIN-CAM) tool. By bringing together three team partners from diverse organisations, the project focuses on FIN-CAM use cases through service design with key stakeholders, which aims at supporting the implementation of the tool in diverse organisations. In addition to the use case report, the project will develop an online demo version of the tool, a policy brief and initiate a cross-country collaboration with Nordic CAM developers and engage international assessment communities to discuss the use of CAMs in researcher assessment.</p>

Mission and objectives. How does the project fits with the overall vision of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment?

The aim of the project is to promote responsible researcher assessment and support the implementation of CoARA commitments by co-piloting the implementation of FIN-CAM (Finnish Career Assessment Matrix) assessment tool. Aligned with the vision of CoARA, FIN-CAM supports the recognition of diverse research contributions, balancing qualitative and quantitative methods, and advancing fair, transparent, and holistic assessment practices. In collaboration with three team partners, the project seeks to contribute to the global conversation on the use of CAMs in researcher assessments and drive lasting change.

The objective of the project is to develop use cases (e.g. recruitment, performance review, competence mapping) for the assessment tool through service design thinking in collaboration with the tool's users (e.g., Finnish HEIs, research funders, research institutes). Service design is a holistic and collaborative approach to co-create best services and solutions, routinely applied by the team members. The project will develop a demo version of the FIN-CAM online tool and foster international dialogue among Nordic CAM developers, informing a policy brief with key insights and recommendations. To ensure mutual learning and exchange of knowledge, the project results will be publicly available both in Finnish and English to ensure accessibility for the CoARA community and beyond.

ARRA core commitments' supported by the Project

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|-------------------------------------|---|
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> | Recognise the diversity of contributions to, and careers in research according to the needs and the nature of the research |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> | Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer-review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> | Abandon inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal and publication-based metrics, in particular inappropriate uses of journal impact factor (JIF) and h-index |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> | Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations in research assessment |

Cascade Funding Call 2: Selected project 15/28

Organisation overview	
<p>University of Bucharest (UB) Bucharest, Romania</p> <p><i>With 19 faculties, over 50 research centers and 9 research units, UB is a well-known institution of excellence in education and research. In recent years, UB focused on promoting actions towards the adoption of CoARA's principles, establishing dedicated working groups at the university level.</i></p> <p>Partner organisations:</p> <p>Universidad Autonoma de Madrid (UAM) Madrid, Spain</p> <p><i>UAM combines academic excellence with a strong commitment to research assessment reform. With over 30,000 students and 3,000 staff, it offers diverse programmes across 8 faculties. UAM is part of CoARA Constitutive Assembly having signed the ARRA in November 2022 and member of Spain NC, and has recently submitted its CoARA Action Plan to further this commitment.</i></p> <p>Aix-Marseille Université (amU) Marseille, France</p> <p><i>amU is one of the largest universities in France with 80000 students and 8000 staff. AMU is composed of 121 research structures, 19 research research institutes, 12 doctoral schools covering all the knowledge fields. AMU is member of CoARA since 2022 and began its assessment reform. AMU is co-piloting the CoARA French National Chapter.</i></p>	

The Project
Type
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Teaming project <input type="checkbox"/> Institutional Pilot Project <input type="checkbox"/> Institutional Change Project
Title
Laboratory of Engagement with Research Assessment Reform (LERAR): exchanging good practices between three members of one European university alliance, CIVIS
Abstract
Encouraging researchers to stay committed to the CoARA principles is a long-time challenge for universities. Local norms and national regulations do not always match with ongoing European and international initiatives, creating a gap that affects especially researchers who are changing institutions as part of

different transnational mobility programmes. Typically, researchers based at one institution must comply with the national criteria in the evaluation of their research outputs, which is not necessarily the case with researchers moving from one institution to another, especially early-stage career researchers who are more prone to change their hosting institution. The increased mobility can also lead to the diversification of research outputs. This double aspect should be recognised in research assessment, and it is our strong conviction that European university alliances are in the best position to address the challenges by: (1) providing training and examples of good practices to all-stage career researchers doing mobilities in other universities of the alliance; (2) identifying new research outputs produced outside of the typical national criteria. The project aims to create a network within CIVIS (<https://civis.eu/en>) to exchange good practices and to accelerate the adoption of CoARA principles within the alliance including worldwide partners.

Mission and objectives. How does the project fits with the overall vision of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment?

The main goal of the project is to promote CoARA in CIVIS, and to explore good practices in research assessment, starting from the three partner universities and creating a larger network within the alliance. In order to achieve this goal, the project will include a detailed comparison through a thorough mapping of the current situation in the partner universities, inviting other members of the CIVIS alliance to share their experiences, and encouraging more universities to adhere to CoARA. LERAR will create a toolkit for other members of the alliance, which will include examples of good practices in light of the CoARA principles, showcasing the different layers of engagement (local, national, and international) with research assessment reform in the case of European universities.

Objectives:

1. Increase the number of signatories inside CIVIS
2. Promote CoARA commitments internationally towards partners
3. Share the good practices at the level of CIVIS and build the sustainability of the transition process to the adoption of the CoARA principles within a university alliance
4. Creation of a common guide and recommendations for promoting CoARA's principles through dedicated actions at the CIVIS level
5. Elaborate methodological recommendations for other Universities alliances

ARRA core commitments' supported by the Project

- Recognise the diversity of contributions to, and careers in research according to the needs and the nature of the research

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer-review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Abandon inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal and publication-based metrics, in particular inappropriate uses of journal impact factor (JIF) and h-index
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations in research assessment

Cascade Funding Call 2: Selected project 16/28

Organisation overview	
<p>Research Data Alliance Association AISBL Brussels, Belgium</p> <p><i>The RDA Association AISBL is the European office of the RDA, tasked with supporting the regional communities and facilitating the connection between national and global initiatives. RDA Europe is built on the strong commitment of the European countries, individuals, organisations, and the European Commission to the mission of the RDA.</i></p> <p><u>Partner organisations:</u></p> <p>Catholic University of Portugal (UCP) Rio de Mouro, Portugal</p> <p><i>Universidade Católica Portuguesa is committed to developing inspiring and innovative medical education closely associated with research, to train health professionals with the skills to generate knowledge, with a deep ethical sense and social responsibility, who will contribute to the continuous improvement of health care and the advancement of the well-being of populations.</i></p> <p>TOBB University of Economics and Technology (TOBB ETÜ) Ankara, Türkiye</p> <p><i>TOBB ETÜ was founded by the Union of Chambers and Commodity Exchanges of Turkey in 2004 with the mission of creating qualified human resources to contribute to the development of national industrial and commercial life. It is among the most prominent universities considering its high quality programs, is aiming to become an international center of excellence.</i></p>	

The Project
Type
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Teaming project <input type="checkbox"/> Institutional Pilot Project <input type="checkbox"/> Institutional Change Project
Title
Teaming for self-evaluation in research assessment across scales: from researchers to institutions
Abstract
This project brings together the Catholic University of Portugal (UCP), TOBB University of Economics and Technology (TOBB ETÜ), and the Research Data Alliance (RDA) to co-develop and implement a structured approach to ethics self-evaluation in research assessment. Centred on the CoARA-ERIP Ethics Self-

Assessment Checklist, the initiative targets reform across four key levels: individual researchers, research projects, research projects, and institutions. The project emphasises the importance of ethical reflection and integrity throughout the research lifecycle, especially in light of artificial intelligence (AI) and data-intensive methods. It supports alignment with CoARA's vision and European policy priorities, including the REA Report on Research Assessment, European Strategy for AI in Science, and the Apply AI Strategy.

AI influences all research stages, demanding rigorous ethical governance, transparency, and respect for fundamental rights. This teaming initiative promotes mutual learning, digital responsibility, and the creation of adaptable tools and training for scalable use. Outputs will serve institutional needs while contributing to broader CoARA goals and be further disseminated through the global RDA network, engaging over 15,000 researchers across 151 countries.

Mission and objectives. How does the project fits with the overall vision of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment?

The mission of “Teaming for self-evaluation in research assessment across scales: from researchers to institutions” is to develop and pilot ethics self-evaluation methods that strengthen responsible, transparent, and policy-aligned research assessment. Using the CoARA-ERIP Ethics Self-Assessment Checklist, the project supports researchers, research units and institutions in enhancing ethical awareness and identifying actionable reforms to improve research quality.

The project will clarify how AI and data-intensive research affect assessment, integrating institutional, national, and international ethical and legal standards. It also promotes open, trustworthy, and interoperable infrastructures to support transparent evaluation and accountability. This work is fully aligned with the ARRA: it recognises diverse contributions and career paths, emphasises the social value of research, and fosters co-construction of knowledge through mutual learning across disciplines and roles.

UCP, TOBB ETÜ, and RDA will jointly produce adaptable multilingual ethical self-assessment templates, case studies, training resources, and guidance. All outputs will be made openly available to the CoARA community and beyond, boosted by dissemination through the global RDA network.

ARRA core commitments' supported by the Project

- Recognise the diversity of contributions to, and careers in research according to the needs and the nature of the research
- Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer-review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators

- | | |
|-------------------------------------|---|
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> | Abandon inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal and publication-based metrics, in particular inappropriate uses of journal impact factor (JIF) and h-index |
| <input type="checkbox"/> | Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations in research assessment |

Cascade Funding Call 2: Selected project 17/28

Organisation overview	
<p>University College Cork (UCC) Cork, Ireland</p> <p><i>UCC is a research-based globally oriented university with over 24,000 students, 3,200 staff and over 200,000 alumni worldwide. It comprises four Colleges: Arts, Celtic Studies & Social Sciences; Business & Law; Medicine & Health; and Science, Engineering & Food Science.</i></p> <p><u>Partner organisation:</u> AmsterdamUMC (AUMC) City, Country</p> <p><i>Amsterdam UMC trains thousands of young people to become doctors, specialists or nurses. Amsterdam UMC has eight research institutes. The researchers affiliated with these are internationally among the top in medical scientific research.</i></p>	<p>Amsterdam UMC</p>

The Project
Type
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Teaming project <input type="checkbox"/> Institutional Pilot Project <input type="checkbox"/> Institutional Change Project
Title
ORFIRA - Introducing an Open Research Framework and integrating Open Research indicators into Research Assessment
Abstract
<p>This project aims to foster knowledge transfer between AmsterdamUMC (AUMC) and University College Cork (UCC) by leveraging Amsterdam's successful implementation of the Dutch Recognition & Rewards program and Open Research (OR) practices. The collaboration will focus on identifying effective OR Practices at AUMC, exploring their benefits for researchers, institutions, the national research ecosystem, and society. Key indicators used for research assessment will be examined to understand how to embed a culture of OR in daily practices. AUMC will provide advisory support to UCC in developing a tailored OR Framework aligned with CoARA principles. This framework will define OR within UCC's context, and identify necessary enabling structures such as awareness, training, infrastructure and with a particular focus on securing senior leadership support. OR indicators will be developed that will inform the transformation of institutional research assessment processes, including recruitment and promotion. Engagement sessions will be held to introduce the framework and its integration into research assessment. Mechanisms for the</p>

future sustainability of project outcomes will be identified, ensuring long-term impact.

Researcher engagement will include baseline data from an ongoing national project, partner visits, consultations, co-creation methodology, and feedback collection. Enabled by our co-leadership of the CoARA National Chapter for Ireland, key learnings from the project will be harnessed to support the embedding of OR and Responsible Research Assessment practices at a sector level.

Mission and objectives. How does the project fits with the overall vision of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment?

This project aims to create knowledge transfer opportunities between Amsterdam UMC and UCC to:

- Learn how AUMC applied the Dutch Recognition & Rewards programme and embedded Open Science practices in their institution and its assessment processes:
 - o Identify Open Research Practices that researchers in Amsterdam engage in successfully
 - o What are the benefits for researchers, the institution, the national research ecosystem and society?
 - o What indicators are used for research assessment?
- Understand how to create a culture of open research where practices are embedded in researchers' day-to-day life
- Harness Amsterdam UMC's expertise in an advisory capacity to UCC in order to develop recommendations for a UCC Open Research Framework (aligned with UCC's CoARA action plan draft)
- Define Open Research in the context of UCC, identify priority items and the required enabling structures: awareness that goes beyond OA, training, infrastructure
- Develop Open Research indicators for UCC – tailored to the context of each of the 4 colleges with a view of integration into research assessment (recruitment/promotion/awards)
- Hold engagement sessions to introduce OR Framework, enablers and integration into research assessment in each college
- Utilize the UMC's experience to develop mechanisms for the future sustainability of the project outcomes and identify next steps

ARRA core commitments' supported by the Project

- Recognise the diversity of contributions to, and careers in research according to the needs and the nature of the research

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer-review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators
<input type="checkbox"/>	Abandon inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal and publication-based metrics, in particular inappropriate uses of journal impact factor (JIF) and h-index
<input type="checkbox"/>	Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations in research assessment

List of the Cascade Funding Call 2 Beneficiaries: Institutional Change Projects

Name of the project	Organisations	Countries	Pages
MUSEVAL – A Framework for Museum-Based Research Evaluation	Museo Galileo – Istituto e Museo di Storia della Scienza	Italy	48
Integrating Open Science into the Qualitative Research Assessment Reform at University Clermont-Auvergne-OSQuAR-UCA	Université Clermont Auvergne	France	50
REACH – REady for lAsting CHange in research assessment at Osnabrück University of Applied Sciences	Osnabrück University of Applied Sciences	Germany	52
CAREER-PILOT: CoARA-Aligned Pathway Pilot at SEAMK	Seinäjoki University of Applied Sciences (SEAMK)	Finland	54
Mind the Gender Gap in Computer Science (MindGenGapICT)	Foundation for Research and Technology Hellas	Greece	56
Non-traditional key output in evidence based CVs for applicants	Dutch Research Organisation (NWO)	Netherlands	58
MERIT-BIH Groups: Institutionalizing Fair and Robust Research Assessment of Research Groups through Infrastructure	Berlin Institute of Health at Charite	Germany	60
THRIVE – Towards holistic and responsible institutional evaluation at IRB Barcelona	Fundació Institut de Recerca Biomèdica (IRB Barcelona)	Spain	62
Pilot Experiments for Innovative Academic Assessment under ANECA's CoARA Action Plan (PEI3AC)	National Agency for Quality Assessment and Accreditation (ANECA)	Spain	64
ARIA – Advancing Responsible and Inclusive Assessment at UEFISCDI	UEFISCDI	Romania	66
Reforming research assessment throughout the employee lifecycle	Dublin City University	Ireland	68

Cascade Funding Call 2: Selected project 18/28

Organisation overview	
<p>Museo Galileo – Istituto e Museo di Storia della Scienza Firenze, Italy</p> <p><i>Museo Galileo is a leading institution in the history of science, combining a major collection of scientific instruments with research, documentation, and dissemination activities. Its museum, library, archives, and labs form an integrated center promoting scientific culture and enhancing Italy's scientific heritage.</i></p>	<p>museo galileo Istituto e Museo di Storia della Scienza</p>

The Project
Type
<input type="checkbox"/> Teaming project <input type="checkbox"/> Institutional Pilot Project <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Institutional Change Project
Title
MUSEVAL – A Framework for Museum-Based Research Evaluation
Abstract
<p>The Museo Galileo, as both a museum and a research centre actively engaged in Open Science, has long been concerned with the recognition and evaluation of its outputs as genuine research products. While research is already an integral part of museum practice—often interdisciplinary, collaborative, and embedded in curatorial, educational, and design activities—it is still rarely acknowledged or assessed on the same terms as academic research. This project aims to address that gap by initiating a process of institutional change within our own organisation, while at the same time developing a scalable and modular framework for museum-based research—one that identifies its specificities, defines appropriate evaluation metrics, and can be adopted by other museums and similar institutions seeking to gain recognition for, and assess the value of, their research activities. By doing so, we aim to enhance the visibility, credibility, and impact of research conducted in museums, while strengthening their role in the third mission of research institutions and fostering closer integration with academic and societal partners.</p>
Mission and objectives. How does the project fits with the overall vision of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment?
<p>The Museo Galileo is one of the foremost international institutions in the History of Science, combining a renowned museum of scientific instruments and a research institution that actively promotes research projects and events. Committed to Open Science, Museo Galileo recognizes the crucial role of museums in making scientific knowledge accessible, aligning with the UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science. This commitment led the museum to sign</p>

the Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information and host the Open Science in and by Museums workshop on May 11, 2023, resulting in a [position paper](#) outlining its vision and ongoing efforts.

In this spirit, Museo Galileo has also joined CoARA, to contribute to the broader debate on museums' role in research and help identify which incentives need rethinking to support their contributions. Museums generate original research through digitization, exhibitions, and public engagement, yet these contributions are often overlooked. In line with the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment, the museum aims to develop a framework and practical tools to evaluate museum-based research. This includes supporting internal decision-making on research projects and career assessment, while externally fostering rigorous evaluation criteria for exhibitions and digital collections, integrating museum research into academic CVs, funding applications, and institutional assessments.

ARRA core commitments' supported by the Project

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|-------------------------------------|---|
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> | Recognise the diversity of contributions to, and careers in research according to the needs and the nature of the research |
| <input type="checkbox"/> | Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer-review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators |
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| <input type="checkbox"/> | Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations in research assessment |

Cascade Funding Call 2: Selected project 19/28

Organisation overview	
<p>Université Clermont Auvergne Clermont-Ferrand, France</p> <p><i>Université Clermont Auvergne (UCA) is a multidisciplinary higher education institution located in Clermont-Ferrand, France. Gathering 40000 students, including almost 5 500 (14%) international ones and 3.800 staff, UCA is composed of 5 doctoral schools and 39 research laboratories. UCA is member of Europe University Association (EUA), is labelled HRS4R and leader of European University ARTEMIS.</i></p>	

The Project
<p>Type</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Teaming project <input type="checkbox"/> Institutional Pilot Project <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Institutional Change Project</p>
<p>Title</p> <p>Integrating Open Science into the Qualitative Research Assessment Reform at University Clermont-Auvergne-OSQuAR-UCA</p>
<p>Abstract</p> <p>Université Clermont Auvergne (UCA) is strongly committed to reforming research assessment by placing open science at the heart of its strategy. The OSQuAR-UCA project seeks to embed open science practices into qualitative assessment processes at all levels—individual, project-based, and institutional. Structured around three phases, the project first promotes a shift in evaluation culture through community-wide engagement, including webinars, workshops, narrative CV training, and the sharing of best practices. In its second phase, UCA will co-develop open science-based assessment criteria with researchers, evaluators, and HR representatives, ensuring recognition of diverse research outputs and alignment with CoARA principles. The final phase focuses on institutionalizing these reforms through revised policies, structured training programs, and integration into UCA’s HRS4R strategy, guaranteeing long-term sustainability. Drawing on leading European examples and contributing to CoARA’s ACA Working Group, OSQuAR-UCA aims to foster a fair, inclusive, and responsible research assessment system. Ultimately, UCA aims to contribute to systemic change by promoting qualitative, open science-based evaluation practices that support greater transparency, equity, and impact within the academic community.</p>
<p>Mission and objectives. How does the project fits with the overall vision of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment?</p>

The OSQuAR-UCA project aims to embed open science practices into research assessment at all levels, including individual assessments (career promotion), project evaluations, and institutional processes, ensuring their recognition as key elements of high-quality research.

The mission of this project directly supports the implementation of the CoARA Agreement and is aligned with the CoARA Agreement's Principles, by focusing on:

1. Developing a qualitative assessment framework that values diverse research outputs (data, software, preprints) and practices (open publication and open data), moving beyond traditional metrics.
2. Providing institutional governance guidelines and practical tools for evaluators and researchers integrating open science criteria into assessments, ensuring applicability and alignment with responsible research practices.

The project directly supports CoARA's commitments, particularly:

- Recognizing diverse contributions by evaluating open science activities (Commitment 1).
- Prioritizing qualitative approaches over journal-based metrics (2-4).
- Advancing equity and transparency through training and clear criteria (5,6, 7 and 10).
- By piloting reforms at UCA, the project will serve as a model for systemic change (5-6-8).
- By proposing to share the outputs and expertise gained with the European Universities, the project fully aligns with one of CoARA's objectives (8-9).

ARRA core commitments' supported by the Project

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Recognise the diversity of contributions to, and careers in research according to the needs and the nature of the research
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer-review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Abandon inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal and publication-based metrics, in particular inappropriate uses of journal impact factor (JIF) and h-index
<input type="checkbox"/>	Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations in research assessment

Cascade Funding Call 2: Selected project 20/28

Organisation overview	 HOCHSCHULE OSNABRÜCK UNIVERSITY OF APPLIED SCIENCES
<p>Osnabrück University of Applied Sciences Osnabrück, Germany</p> <p><i>Osnabrück University of Applied Sciences is the most research-intensive university of applied sciences in Lower Saxony, with good networking in business, society and the scientific community. The research and transfer strength is one of the outstanding features in terms of scope, breadth and quality.</i></p>	

The Project
Type
<input type="checkbox"/> Teaming project <input type="checkbox"/> Institutional Pilot Project <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Institutional Change Project
Title
REACH - REady for lAsting CHange in research assessment at Osnabrück University of Applied Sciences
Abstract
<p>The REACH project at Osnabrück University of Applied Sciences (OS UAS) aims to transform research assessment by creating a comprehensive toolbox including qualitative and quantitative criteria. Leveraging the university's tradition of bottom-up decision-making, REACH focuses on enhancing transparency, inclusiveness, and collaboration through an iterative development process involving researchers and specialists. The project will see the development, testing, and refinement of assessment criteria applicable across various research domains, enhancing relevance and facilitating adoption. Through workshops, surveys, and testing, REACH will ensure that the criteria are robust and adaptable, contributing insights to be shared openly beyond the university. This initiative strengthens OS UAS' commitment to progressive research assessment, with the toolbox serving as a dynamic and sustainable model for institutional change. REACH also aims to provide a reference for other institutions considering similar reforms and will support the reform of research assessment in related educational and scientific discussions and initiatives.</p>
Mission and objectives. How does the project fits with the overall vision of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment?
<p>Osnabrück University of Applied Sciences (OS UAS) is embarking on a transformative journey to reform research assessment through the REACH project. Drawing from its rich history of participatory decision-making, the university aims to create an innovative toolbox of qualitative and quantitative assessment criteria, fostering transparency, inclusiveness, and collaboration in</p>

research assessment. The mission of REACH is to enrich research assessment practices within the university by increasing the number of criteria adhering to the ARRA principles, engaging researchers and specialists in a bottom-up and iterative process. The objectives include developing and testing a comprehensive set of assessment criteria that are both relevant and practical, actively promoting cultural change across the institution. This project goes beyond current community efforts by ensuring the realized criteria are applicable across various research fields and fostering an environment conducive to lasting institutional change. REACH aims to share the acquired knowledge broadly, benefiting not only OS UAS' internal practices but offering a reference for other institutions to explore similar reforms.

ARRA core commitments' supported by the Project

- | | |
|-------------------------------------|---|
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> | Recognise the diversity of contributions to, and careers in research according to the needs and the nature of the research |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> | Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer-review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> | Abandon inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal and publication-based metrics, in particular inappropriate uses of journal impact factor (JIF) and h-index |
| <input type="checkbox"/> | Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations in research assessment |

Cascade Funding Call 2: Selected project 21/28

Organisation overview	
<p>Seinäjoki University of Applied Sciences (SEAMK) Seinäjoki, Finland</p> <p><i>Seinäjoki University of Applied Sciences (SEAMK) is a multidisciplinary higher education and RDI institution. With about 6,000 students in six fields of education, 200 teachers, 100 people working in RDI and 100 other staff members, SEAMK conducts RDI supporting teaching and enterprises and services in the region.</i></p>	

The Project
Type
<input type="checkbox"/> Teaming project <input type="checkbox"/> Institutional Pilot Project <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Institutional Change Project
Title
CAREER-PILOT: CoARA-Aligned Pathway Pilot at SEAMK
Abstract
<p>The project develops and pilots two CoARA-aligned frameworks to strengthen responsible research assessment at SEAMK. First, it will create a career path model for non-doctoral researchers and lecturers, providing a clear structure for progression based on diverse contributions in teaching, RDI, impact and service. Second, it will expand the current principal lecturer evaluation template to align fully with CoARA criteria, incorporating open science, leadership and societal engagement indicators.</p> <p>Both models will be co-designed with staff across career stages; piloted through real appraisal and evaluation processes; and refined based on feedback from users, HR and external reviewers. Parallel to this, SEAMK will lead a benchmarking group with 5–10 Finnish and European partner universities to test the models' transferability.</p> <p>Outputs include openly licensed frameworks, practical starter kits for other UASs, and recommendations for institutional adoption. The project fits fully within the Cascade Funding pilot category; it pilots specific, scalable changes that enhance transparency, fairness and diversity in research assessment, while providing reusable tools for the broader CoARA community.</p>
Mission and objectives. How does the project fits with the overall vision of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment?
<p>The project aims to strengthen SEAMK's career development and evaluation practices in line with the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment (CoARA). The main objectives are to:</p>

1. create and pilot career path models for non-doctoral researchers and lecturers, and
2. develop and pilot a more comprehensive evaluation model for principal lecturers based on CoARA criteria.

SEAMK already has a tenure track model for doctoral researchers and a principal lecturer monitoring process since 2017; however, both need further development to align fully with CoARA's principles of recognizing diverse contributions, qualitative assessment, and broader impact.

The project will deliver two concrete frameworks: a new career pathway for non-doctoral staff and an expanded evaluation model for principal lecturers. Both will be developed through staff workshops, piloted, evaluated, and refined within a twelve-month timeframe.

Parallel to this, SEAMK will lead a benchmarking network with 5–10 Finnish and European partner institutions to exchange experiences and validate the models internationally.

This approach is fully aligned with CoARA's vision: it strengthens institutional practices for recognising a wide range of research, education and impact activities; emphasises qualitative, peer-informed evaluation; and supports mutual learning and transfer of good practices across institutions. The outputs; clear frameworks, pilot data, and open sharing of lessons learned, directly support systemic, scalable change as envisaged in the Agreement.

ARRA core commitments' supported by the Project

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Recognise the diversity of contributions to, and careers in research according to the needs and the nature of the research
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer-review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Abandon inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal and publication-based metrics, in particular inappropriate uses of journal impact factor (JIF) and h-index
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations in research assessment

Cascade Funding Call 2: Selected project 22/28

Organisation overview	
<p>Foundation for Research and Technology Hellas (FORTH) Heraklion, Greece</p> <p><i>FORTH is the largest research center in Greece with well-organized facilities and a reputation as a top-level research institution worldwide. FORTH comprises of ten Research Institutes the largest of which is the Institute of Computer Science (FORTH-ICS) playing a leading role, in Greece and internationally, in the field of ICT.</i></p>	

The Project
Type
<input type="checkbox"/> Teaming project <input type="checkbox"/> Institutional Pilot Project <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Institutional Change Project
Title
Mind the Gender Gap in Computer Science (MindGenGapICT)
Abstract
<p>MindGenGapICT is an institutional change project for promoting Diversity, Inclusivity and Gender Equality (DIE) at the Institute of Computer Science of the Foundation for Research and Technology – Hellas (FORTH-ICS). Its primary objective is to analyse the current state of gender representation at the Institute and to design targeted, evidence-based measures addressing structural and cultural imbalances in a gradual and sustainable manner.</p> <p>MindGenGapICT will address key questions such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How does gender imbalance affect internal research processes? - Can gender balancing improve research assessment processes? - How can reformation be measured, verified and sustained? <p>Key activities include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reviewing existing data to identify patterns and gaps - Mapping best practices - Designing feasible interventions tailored to FORTH-ICS based on best practices and FORTH's Gender Equality Plan - Communicating findings, recommendations and awareness-raising activities within FORTH-ICS. <p>MindGenGapICT will deliver a targeted roadmap to FORTH-ICS leadership, offering effective, evident-based recommendations, adaptation strategies and follow-up plans.</p> <p>By focusing on feasible actions and sustained engagement, a gradual cultural shift towards a more inclusive research environment will be established, in alignment with institutional and European efforts to promote DIE in research</p>

settings. The anticipated outcomes include more equitable and inclusive assessment practices, improved research quality, and a reduction in systemic biases.

Mission and objectives. How does the project fits with the overall vision of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment?

The mission of MindGenGapICT project is to generate guidelines for interventions and policies for realistic, time-bound transformations of the institutional setup for smoothing out gender disparities in workforce composition, governance structure and research practice at the Institute of Computer Science of FORTH (FORTH-ICS).

The key objectives are: 1. to identify root causes of gender imbalance through analysis of existing gender-related quantitative and qualitative data 2. to propose and apply interventions to smooth disparities 3. to ensure long-lasting transformation.

The primary outcome will be an insightful roadmap document to FORTH-ICS leadership, providing effective, evident-based recommendations, adaptation and follow-up plan.

The expected impact includes: 1. improved gender representation within both research teams and administrative bodies at FORTH-ICS 2. integration of the gender dimension into the research practice and outcomes 3. formulation of policies and implementation of interventions aimed at long-term transformation 4. development of methods for assessi3. formulationning the transformation process.

By engaging personnel across all levels, MindGenGapICT builds internal capacity and lays the foundation for sustained transformation that brings FORTH-ICS closer to the commitments of the CoARA Agreement, particularly shifting towards qualitative, inclusive and context-sensitive evaluation criteria. Additionally, it could serve as a replicable model for driving systemic change in STEM-focused environments.

ARRA core commitments' supported by the Project

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|-------------------------------------|---|
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> | Recognise the diversity of contributions to, and careers in research according to the needs and the nature of the research |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> | Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer-review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators |
| <input type="checkbox"/> | Abandon inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal and publication-based metrics, in particular inappropriate uses of journal impact factor (JIF) and h-index |
| <input type="checkbox"/> | Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations in research assessment |

Cascade Funding Call 2: Selected project 23/28

Organisation overview	
<p>Dutch Research Organisation (NWO) The Hague, Netherlands</p> <p><i>The Dutch Research Council (NWO) is one of the most important science funding bodies in the Netherlands. NWO invests almost 1 billion euros annually in curiosity-driven research, research related to societal challenges and research infrastructure.</i></p>	

The Project
Type
<input type="checkbox"/> Teaming project <input type="checkbox"/> Institutional Pilot Project <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Institutional Change Project
Title
Non-traditional key output in evidence based CVs for applicants
Abstract
<p>In its effort to encourage the recognition and reward of a wider range of accomplishments of applicants, NWO has introduced a CV format that limits the number of outputs an applicant can list, and encourages the inclusion of nontraditional output. In this project we will explore whether and how applicants list non-traditional outputs in the narrative CV NWO works with since 2020. We will analyse the CVs of applicants in NWO's Talent Programme over a period of five years, across disciplines and seniority of the applicant. This will provide insight into the use of the opportunities the CV format provides, whether this affects funding chances and will allow us to make recommendations to NWO and other organisations working with narrative CVs or are interested in doing so. We will share our results with relevant parties within NWO, but also with other CoARA partners and interested international organisations active in the field of research funding. We will also publish a research paper to share our results widely.</p>
Mission and objectives. How does the project fits with the overall vision of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment?
<p>This proposal focusses on a key element of research assessment reform initiatives: the possibility for researchers to be assessed on a diverse range of outputs. Through use of its narrative CV, the Dutch Research Council promotes greater variety in how researchers can present their achievements and encourages a wider recognition of those diverse achievements. However, at this point it is unclear to what extent this option is used by applicants and whether this openness is embraced by their assessors.</p> <p>Our proposed project connects directly to the vision of ARRA-agreement, which calls upon signatories to recognise the diversity of contributions by researchers.</p>

We will undertake this project based on solid evidence, using a unique dataset of thousands of narrative CVs from a five-year period. This also allows us to investigate whether this varies across disciplines and by seniority of applicants. Our aim is to effect change within our own organisation and provide practical recommendations for organisations looking to introduce or improve their practices in this area.

ARRA core commitments' supported by the Project

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Recognise the diversity of contributions to, and careers in research according to the needs and the nature of the research
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer-review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators
<input type="checkbox"/>	Abandon inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal and publication-based metrics, in particular inappropriate uses of journal impact factor (JIF) and h-index
<input type="checkbox"/>	Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations in research assessment

Cascade Funding Call 2: Selected project 24/28

Organisation overview	
<p>Berlin Institute of Health at Charite Berlin, Germany</p> <p><i>The Berlin Institute of Health at Charité (BIH) is a biomedical research institution dedicated to advancing translational medicine and responsible research practices. As the translational research arm of Charité – Universitätsmedizin Berlin, BIH bridges basic science and clinical application. It fosters innovation through open science, data stewardship, and stakeholder engagement.</i></p>	

The Project
<p>Type</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Teaming project <input type="checkbox"/> Institutional Pilot Project <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Institutional Change Project</p>
<p>Title</p> <p>MERIT-BIH Groups: Institutionalizing Fair and Robust Research Assessment of Research Groups through Infrastructure</p>
<p>Abstract</p> <p>The MERIT Portal is a web-based tool developed at the Berlin Institute of Health (BIH) at Charité to support transparent, fair, and quality-driven professorial appointments (https://merit-portal.charite.de/). This proposal seeks to expand its use beyond professorships to evaluate internal research groups—creating MERIT-BIH Groups.</p> <p>Aligned with the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment and CoARA principles, this initiative promotes research quality, openness, and societal relevance. BIH and Charité have already developed a CoARA-aligned action plan, but sustainable reform requires supportive infrastructure tailored to workflows and stakeholder needs. MERIT-BIH Groups will provide that structure, enabling reflexive, fair, and mission-driven performance evaluations.</p> <p>Key deliverables include adapted templates (e.g., based on a structured narrative CV tool https://merit-cv.charite.de/), piloted evaluation cycles, and integration with existing reporting systems. A longitudinal component will enable tracking research group progress over time. Outcomes will guide institutional learning, support, and strategy, while also contributing to the CoARA ecosystem through shared tools and practices.</p> <p>Although supported by BIH leadership, implementation currently lacks dedicated internal funding, highlighting the need for external support to move from concept to practice.</p>

Mission and objectives. How does the project fits with the overall vision of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment?

The MERIT-BIH Groups project aims to create a structured, participatory, and mission-driven framework for evaluating research groups at the Berlin Institute of Health (BIH) at Charité. Building on the existing MERIT Portal—originally developed to support fair, transparent professorial appointments (<https://merit-portal.charite.de/>)—this initiative will adapt the platform for internal evaluation of research groups, promoting institutional learning and strategic coherence.

Our mission is to embed a quality- and impact-oriented as well as inclusive assessment culture across BIH. To achieve this, we will co-design and pilot reporting and assessment templates and tools within the MERIT Portal, enabling structured feedback, cross-group comparison, and data-informed development across the institution.

Outputs include adapted assessment templates (e.g., structured narrative CVs (<https://merit-cv.charite.de/>), piloted evaluation cycles, and a digital tool integrated with existing workflows. A longitudinal feature will allow for tracking group performance over time.

These outputs directly support the goals of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment and implement CoARA principles: qualitative peer review, recognition of diverse contributions, responsible use of metrics, and inclusivity across disciplines and career stages. MERIT-BIH Groups will foster transparency, fairness, and mission alignment in research assessment, contributing to sustainable institutional change and serving as a model for broader implementation.

ARRA core commitments' supported by the Project

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|-------------------------------------|---|
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> | Recognise the diversity of contributions to, and careers in research according to the needs and the nature of the research |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> | Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer-review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> | Abandon inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal and publication-based metrics, in particular inappropriate uses of journal impact factor (JIF) and h-index |
| <input type="checkbox"/> | Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations in research assessment |

Cascade Funding Call 2: Selected project 25/28

Organisation overview	
<p>Fundació Institut de Recerca Biomèdica (IRB Barcelona) Barcelona, Spain</p> <p><i>Leading institution in basic and applied biomedical research. IRB's scientific excellence has been recognised with the Severo Ochoa Centre of Excellence distinction by Spanish government four times. Home to over 400 researchers from 40 different nationalities, IRB has held the HRS4R award since 2014.</i></p>	

The Project
<p>Type</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Teaming project <input type="checkbox"/> Institutional Pilot Project <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Institutional Change Project</p>
<p>Title</p> <p>THRIVE - Towards holistic and responsible institutional evaluation at IRB Barcelona</p>
<p>Abstract</p> <p>THRIVE proposes an in-depth analysis for a structural reform of research talent evaluation practices within IRB Barcelona, in alignment with the principles of Coalition on Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA). The aim is to improve the current model to a more holistic, responsible, and context-sensitive framework that values diversity of research contributions, including mentoring, societal impact, Open Science, and research integrity in a structured manner. THRIVE will assess how to integrate a balanced use of quantitative and qualitative indicators with a focus on the quality and impact of research. Emphasis will be placed on peer review, narrative CVs, and discipline-specific panels rather than solely relying on publication metrics. The analysis will involve a participatory process that includes researchers at all career stages, external experts, and cross-institutional peer visits to review current practices and identify opportunities for reform. Capacity-building activities will support a cultural change within the institution. The findings will inform a roadmap for embedding the revised framework into key institutional processes such as advancements, researcher evaluations, and recruitment procedures, with outputs including tools, templates, and case studies for sustainability. This project represents a commitment to evidence-based institutional change, contributing to the broader European transformation of research assessment practices.</p>
<p>Mission and objectives. How does the project fits with the overall vision of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment?</p>

THRIVE's mission is to conduct an in-depth internal assessment of current talent evaluation processes at IRB Barcelona and develop a comprehensive proposal that outlines how a more holistic and responsible framework—integrating diversity, transparency, and Open Science—can be implemented in the future, through: (1) Co-creation and Assessment: Engage internal stakeholders and external experts to review current evaluation dimensions, tools, and processes, and identify areas for enhancement, (2) Enhanced Evaluation Methods: Assess how existing quantitative metrics can be complemented by robust qualitative, peer-reviewed assessments to achieve balanced and comprehensive evaluations, (3) Capacity Building: Conduct a workshop and one training session for staff and researchers to raise awareness about alternative evaluation models and gather feedback on current practices, including sessions led by international experts, (4) Integration Roadmap: Develop a detailed roadmap and set of recommendations to embed the revised framework into key institutional processes, such as career advancement (promotions), researcher evaluations, and recruitment procedures, and (5) Knowledge Sharing: Produce case studies, tools, and templates based on the internal assessment that can be used for mutual learning and future reform implementation across institutions. This initiative fully aligns with CoARA's vision by providing evidence-based insights and recommendations to advance research assessment practices that are fair, inclusive, and meaningful across disciplines.

ARRA core commitments' supported by the Project	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Recognise the diversity of contributions to, and careers in research according to the needs and the nature of the research
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer-review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Abandon inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal and publication-based metrics, in particular inappropriate uses of journal impact factor (JIF) and h-index
<input type="checkbox"/>	Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations in research assessment

Cascade Funding Call 2: Selected project 26/28

Organisation overview	
<p>National Agency for Quality Assessment and Accreditation (ANECA, Agencia Nacional de Evaluación de la Calidad y Acreditación)</p> <p>Madrid, Spain</p> <p><i>ANECA is responsible for evaluating academic and research institutions in Spain. It plays a key role in shaping policies and frameworks for higher education assessment, ensuring transparency, fairness, and alignment with European standards.</i></p>	

The Project
<p>Type</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Teaming project</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Institutional Pilot Project</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Institutional Change Project</p>
<p>Title</p> <p>Pilot Experiments for Innovative Academic Assessment under ANECA's CoARA Action Plan (PEI3AC)</p>
<p>Abstract</p> <p>This proposal seeks funding to design and execute structured pilot experiments aimed at testing innovative methodologies in research assessment. The project will explore the adoption of narrative CVs, examining how they influence evaluator decision-making compared to traditional formats. It will also assess the feasibility of qualitative assessment models as alternatives to citation-based metrics, focusing on ways to prioritise research quality and contributions over numerical indicators. In addition, the project will implement and evaluate bias mitigation strategies to enhance fairness and inclusivity in research evaluation processes.</p> <p>By conducting controlled pilot studies in collaboration with international researchers and with the participation of academic evaluators and institutions, this initiative will generate empirical evidence and actionable insights that inform the development of a validated framework for systemic academic assessment reform. The findings will support ANECA's ongoing efforts to advance responsible research assessment practices, ensuring greater alignment with CoARA's commitments to fairness, inclusivity, and transparency. Through this initiative, ANECA will contribute to the institutional adoption of improved assessment frameworks across Spain and Europe, fostering a shift towards more equitable and qualitative evaluation systems. The project's outcomes will also provide a foundation for wider policy discussions within the European research community, supporting long-term structural change in academic evaluation.</p>

Mission and objectives. How does the project fits with the overall vision of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment?

This project explores and evaluates experimental methodologies for academic assessment, focusing on narrative CVs, qualitative over quantitative evaluation, and unconscious bias mitigation. Anchored in a strong academic foundation and connected to international collaboration regarding research-on-research, this initiative aims to build empirically grounded frameworks aligned with ANECA's commitments under CoARA.

Through structured pilot studies and a high-volume engagement of evaluators across diverse disciplinary and institutional contexts, the project will assess how narrative CVs influence decision-making, the feasibility of transitioning from metric-based to qualitative evaluation, and the effectiveness of bias mitigation strategies. The findings will provide data-driven insights and validated frameworks to inform institutional reforms, supporting a shift towards responsible research assessment. The project's key objectives are to:

- Develop and pilot innovative academic assessment methodologies that promote fairness and inclusivity.
- Generate evidence-based insights into the effectiveness of narrative CVs, qualitative assessment, and bias mitigation strategies.
- Provide actionable recommendations for institutional adoption of these methodologies.

By providing tested tools, policy recommendations, and implementation strategies, the project will empower ANECA and other institutions to adopt more inclusive and qualitative assessment models, strengthening Spain's and Europe's leadership in responsible research evaluation.

ARRA core commitments' supported by the Project

- | | |
|-------------------------------------|---|
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> | Recognise the diversity of contributions to, and careers in research according to the needs and the nature of the research |
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Cascade Funding Call 2: Selected project 27/28

Organisation overview	
<p>UEFISCDI – Executive Agency for Higher Education, Research, Development and Innovation Funding Bucharest, Romania</p> <p><i>UEFISCDI is Romania's main funder for competitive research. It also advises on science, innovation, and higher education policy. The agency operates under the Ministry of Education and Research. It funds both exploratory and applied research across all fields.</i></p>	<p>Executive Agency for Higher Education, Research, Development and Innovation Funding</p>

The Project
Type
<input type="checkbox"/> Teaming project <input type="checkbox"/> Institutional Pilot Project <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Institutional Change Project
Title
ARIA – Advancing Responsible and Inclusive Assessment at UEFISCDI
Abstract
<p>UEFISCDI, Romania's main funding agency for competitive research and an early signatory of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment (ARRA), proposes this institutional change project to accelerate the adoption of CoARA principles in its internal assessment processes.</p> <p>The project focuses on four main objectives: (1) review and provide recommendations for the alignment of assessment practices in three major funding calls; (2) revise and update internal reviewer guidelines to promote qualitative evaluation and responsible use of quantitative indicators; (3) support the use and understanding of narrative CVs; and (4) develop a shared blueprint on recognizing diverse research impacts, including societal and policy contributions.</p> <p>All activities are designed with a strong participatory approach, involving researchers at all career stages and internal staff through co-creation workshops, consultations, and public events. Outputs will include practical, reusable materials and guidance documents made openly available via the UEFISCDI website, Zenodo, and the BrainMap platform, and other platforms.</p> <p>The project contributes directly to several ARRA commitments and builds on existing pilots, while creating the institutional conditions for long-term, systemic change. Its results will support internal reform and serve as a resource for other funding bodies and institutions advancing responsible research assessment.</p>
Mission and objectives. How does the project fits with the overall vision of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment?

UEFISCDI, Romania's main funder for competitive research and early signatory of ARRA, seeks through this project to institutionalize CoARA-aligned research assessment practices. Building on its role as both funder and policy adviser, and on previous results obtained, the project aims to accelerate systemic and sustainable change across core funding programs that it manages and internal evaluation processes. The project focuses on four interlinked objectives:

1. conduct a comprehensive review of internal research assessment processes across selected funding calls, leading to actionable recommendations.
2. revise internal guidelines for reviewers, embedding qualitative evaluation and the responsible use of metrics.
3. support the uptake of narrative CV formats to better reflect diverse research contributions and career paths.
4. Support the recognition of societal impacts and knowledge valorisation by developing a blueprint on research impacts tailored to UEFISCDI's funding context and to a shared understanding at the level of the entire research community

Together, these objectives embody CoARA's vision of recognizing a broader range of research contributions and promoting qualitative, context related evaluation practices.

Through internal consultation, community engagement, and open dissemination of results, the project will not only anchor change within UEFISCDI but also impact the entire research community in Romania and beyond.

ARRA core commitments' supported by the Project

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Cascade Funding Call 2: Selected project 28/28

Organisation overview	<p>Ollscoil Chathair Bhaile Átha Cliath Dublin City University</p>
<p>Dublin City University Dublin, Ireland</p> <p><i>DCU is proud to be one of the world's leading Young Universities, with a mission to transform lives and societies. Through education, research and innovation, we are focused on delivering real impact, and addressing global challenges in collaboration with our partners and stakeholders.</i></p>	

The Project
Type
<input type="checkbox"/> Teaming project <input type="checkbox"/> Institutional Pilot Project <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Institutional Change Project
Title
Reforming research assessment throughout the employee lifecycle
Abstract
<p>As a signatory of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment (ARRA), and a member of the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (COARA), DCU is committed to being a place that nurtures discovery and to developing a culture of open, transparent, merit-based assessment of research. Institutional commitment to this important movement is evident via the 2021 launch of a DCU Statement on Responsible Use of Research Metrics, setting out 7 guiding principles for those using research metrics for assessment purposes to ensure a nuanced and balanced approach. The recent DCU Strategy (2023–2028) also highlights it as a key objective for the Research pillar and includes the aim to “Build a strengthened research culture consistent with the CoARA principles.”</p> <p>This project aligns with the above commitments and endeavours to further embed a culture of fair and equitable assessment in the University. Training resources will be developed which will allow DCU to upskill and train all ‘assessors’ of research/ers. This ambitious project will reform how research is assessed throughout the employee lifecycle, including job applications, shortlisting, interviews, probation reviews, promotion competitions, and personal development reviews.</p>
Mission and objectives. How does the project fits with the overall vision of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment?
<p>“Reforming research assessment throughout the employee lifecycle” will lead to a significant step change in how assessment of research is viewed and guided across DCU, at all stages of a researcher’s career path further enabling a culture</p>

of open research practice. The project is a collaboration between DCU People (HR), the Open Research Steering Group and the DCU research community. This project speaks to the vision of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment, seeking to maximise the quality and impact of research through the recognition of diverse outputs and activities, achieved through inclusive processes prioritising qualitative assessment practices, addressing the actions of the DCU CoARA Action Plan. The objective is to develop both disciplinary and process relevant guidance, training and support materials for assessors and subjects of research assessment to ensure consistent, fair and equitable approaches are taken irrespective of career stage or discipline area. Training resources will be developed based on gap analysis and liaison with international peers. The resources will reflect best practice and a focus on the CoARA principles, providing the tools and knowledge to assess primarily on qualitative judgement, across multiple research performance indicators for which peer-review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators.

ARRA core commitments' supported by the Project

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Recognise the diversity of contributions to, and careers in research according to the needs and the nature of the research
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